

Review of Better Economics for the Earth [Online Book Club]

Eagle Adastra

Aug 28, 2024

Following is an official [OnlineBookClub.org](https://www.onlinebookclub.org) review of "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories" by Quan-Hoang Vuong, Minh-Hoang Nguyen.

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by Eagle Adastra » 28 Aug 2024, 18:02

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The book "Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories" describes the disaster that awaits the world for lack of caution. It also examines the global population, the result of bad human practices in the lives of everything in the world, the issues

Eagle Adastra
Book of the Month Participant

Posts: 114
Joined: 27 Jun 2024, 16:07
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[Book Review]

The book “Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories” describes the disaster that awaits the world for lack of caution. It also examines the global population, the result of bad human practices in the lives of everything in the world, the issues in Antarctica, the deforestation rate and its impact on the world, the global emission and the energy sector, waste management, the significance of waste management to the health, demise of seagrass,

How does the current global economic system operate? What are their values? What is the fundamental notion of mainstream economists? Who are the mainstream economists? What are the other biotic and abiotic systems, and how do they affect human society? How should the global economy be run? What are the beliefs of Neoclassical economists? What is the creative destruction process? Readers will find the answers in the book “Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories” by Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen.

I like the narrative. It is expository, informational, insightful, explanatory, educational, resourceful, and vast. The process of addressing the global problem is one of the positive aspects of the book. It explains how innovation can serve as a tool for economic growth and efficient improvement in our world. The book title is also positive. It effectively conveys the core message.

There are no negative aspects to the book. The presentation is excellent. The message is detailed. I do not dislike the book. The author is so precise with the ideas and themes in the book. The editing is good.

“Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories” by Quan-Hoang Vuong and Minh-Hoang Nguyen is an eye-opener to many aspects of my life and existence. I rate the book 5 out of 5 stars. I would recommend it to economic analysts. Young adults will learn from the book.

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\**Editorial note*: The piece is an official review on the Online Book Club [1] for the new title [2] and is not edited. A closely related expansion is also provided in the short paper [3]. Interested readers can also read the previous review by Professor Nancy K. Napier [4].

## References

- [1] Aداstra E. (2024). Review of Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories. <https://forums.onlinebookclub.org/viewtopic.php?p=2669785>
- [2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>
- [3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOARN>
- [4] Napier NK. (2024). A power-packed treatise on economics and the environment. <https://mindsponge.info/posts/327>

